

Investigations on Cod Liver Oil Emulsions. Antagonism of Emulsifying Agents.

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It is well known that there are two types of emulsions, one oil in water, the other water in oil emulsion. For each type of emulsion, there are characteristic emulsifiers which promote the formation of only one type of emulsion. Thus, alkali metal soaps, gum acacia, lecithin, etc., produce O-W emulsion and calcium soap, cholesterol, carbon powder, etc., produce W-O emulsion. When emulsifiers producing opposite types of emulsions are mixed together, their mutual effect is antagonistic. The type of the emulsion depends on the relative wetting power of the two phases, oil and water, with respect to the emulsifying agent and on the surface potential of the membrane between the two phases.

Apart from the antagonistic effect leading to reversal of phases, there are cases of antagonism amongst emulsifiers which individually produce the same type of emulsion, but when these are mixed together they break the emulsion. Such cases have, however, drawn little attention upto now and the mechanism of such effects is very little understood. There are only a few stray cases mentioned in the literature.

In the course of investigation on the preparation of emulsion of Cod Liver Oil for pharmaceutical purposes several interesting cases of the above type of antagonism of emulsifiers were observed. Most striking results were obtained with bile salts and gum acacia. Both bile salts and gum acacia when present alone, produce stable O-W emulsion; but when these are present together the emulsion does not form at all. In the cases of turkey-red oil, lecithin and sodium oleate, it was found that when mixed with gum acacia, the emulsion formed liberates oil slowly at the top although when gum acacia is present alone, no such separation is observed. Gelatin, egg-albumin, saponin, Irish moss, agar agar and gum tragacanth when mixed with gum acacia, instead of causing liberation of oil, stabilise the emulsion to that effect.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Emulsifying agents.

Gum acacia—Merck, extra white fine powder B. P.

Irish moss—Merck. The moss was cut to fine pieces and then boiled with distilled water for one hour. The boiled mixture was kept overnight and then strained through fine muslin cloth.

Gelatin—Merck, Gold label. Dissolved in distilled water at 60°

Egg-albumin—Merck. Dry scales were triturated with oil till finely dispersed

Turkey-red oil—Prepared in the laboratory from pure castor oil.

Bile salt—Prepared in the laboratory from ox-bile and purified.

Lecithin—Merck. ex ovo.

Sodium oleate—Prepared in the laboratory from reagent quality caustic soda (Merck) and oleic acid (Merck).

Agar agar—White shreds cut into small pieces and then boiled in water to dissolve.

Gum tragacanth—Merck. Albissima.

Saponin.—Merck. Pure white.

In all cases of emulsification, 35 c.c. of pure Norwegian Cod Liver Oil were mixed with 70 c.c. of water. Emulsifiers, like gum acacia, gum tragacanth and egg-albumin were mixed with oil and the other emulsifiers were mixed with water before emulsification. In the case of agar agar, hot solution was employed. On cooling, the emulsion set to a gel. The gel was gently shaken when the normal fluidity was obtained.

Preliminary mixing was done in the mortar and then the coarse emulsion was passed through 'Primier' colloid mill rotating at 3000 r.p.m. at a clearance of 0.003 inch. In all cases the emulsions were passed through the mill three times.

TABLE I.

Emulsions not liberating oil at the top.

Gum acacia.	Irish moss.	Remarks.
0.0%	0.5%	Thick, water separates slowly.
1.0	0.5	Less thick, water separates less slowly.
1.5	0.5	Less thick, water separates rapidly.

TABLE I (contd.).

Agar agar.		Remarks.
Gum acacia		
0.0	0.4%	Very thick, coarse, water separates.
1.0	0.4	Thick, less coarse, water separates slowly.
2.0	0.4	Less thick, little or no water separates.
4%	0.4%	Thin, water separates rapidly.
Traga.		
0	0.4%	Coarse emulsion.
0	0.6	Very thick, coarse.
0	0.8	Coarse, W-O emulsion.
Gum Traga		
1	0.4	Less coarse, water separates very slowly.
2	0.6	Do Do Do
4	0.6	Less thick, water separates rapidly.
4	0.8	Thick, water separates very slowly.
Gelatin.		
0	0.16%	Very thin, water separates rapidly.
1.5	0.08	Do Do
1.5	0.16	Very thin, thickness on keeping, water separates rapidly.
1.5	0.4	Do Do
Egg-albumin.		
0	0.1%	Very thin, water separates rapidly.
1	0.1	Do Do
1	1.0	Do thickness on keeping.
Saponin.		
0	0.04%	Very thin, water separates rapidly.
1	0.04	Do Do

With gelatin, egg-albumin and saponin, the consistency was always thin but the particles became finer with increase of concentration of

the emulsifiers. With 0.4% gelatin, the emulsion on keeping assumed a curd-like appearance.

TABLE II.

Emulsions where oil separates at the top.

Gum acacia.	Turkey-red oil.	Remarks.
0%	0.75%	Very thin, oil separates slowly from the beginning.
1	1.0	Do Do less Do
Bile salt.		
0	0.1%	Coarse, very thin, oil separates slowly from the beginning.
0	0.5	Less coarse, Do Do
*0	1.0	Fine, less thin, Do, Do, very slowly, Do
1	0.05	Very thin, oil separates slowly from the beginning.
*1	0.1	Less thin, Do Do
1	0.2	Breaks immediately.
1	0.5	Do
2	0.5	Do
5	0.5	Do
10	1.0	Do
Lecithin.		
0	0.1%	Very thin, oil separates rapidly.
0	0.5	Less thin Do Do
2	0.1	Do Do
2	0.5	Do oil separates slowly
Na-oleate.		
0	0.2%	Thin, oil separates slowly.
2	0.2	Do Do

Except in the cases marked with asterisk, all emulsions are thin and water separates at the bottom rapidly.

DISCUSSION.

It is well known that for easy emulsification of the O-W type, the surface tension or the internal viscosity of the dispersion medium should be low. Emulsifiers like sodium oleate, bile salts, turkey-red oil, etc., lower the surface tension and they facilitate emulsification. But emulsions produced by these emulsifiers are not stable over longer periods except under special circumstances. As soon as mechanical or thermal agitation is stopped, the oil globules have a tendency to meet together and accumulate at the top. The film formed on the particles gradually gets thinner and thinner, a direct effect of low surface tension, and ultimately the film ruptures liberating free oil. With emulsifiers like saponin and egg-albumin, the film is not easily broken. These emulsifiers have got a low internal viscosity which facilitates emulsification but the surface tension being high, the film round the oil particles does not easily break. Saponin, as an emulsifier, has this defect that the low internal viscosity of the medium produces a thin emulsion and the covered oil particles float up leaving water at the bottom. Emulsifiers like gum acacia, gum tragacanth, Irish moss, etc., offer high internal viscosity and also high surface tension. Consequently emulsification with these agents is not easily obtained. But once the emulsion is formed the particles can neither coalesce nor float up.

The emulsifiers are classified broadly into three groups : (i) Emulsifiers with low internal and superficial viscosity like sodium oleate; (ii) Emulsifiers with low internal and high superficial viscosity like saponin; (iii) Emulsifiers with high internal and superficial viscosity like gum acacia.

It is evident that although low surface tension enhances adsorption, the adsorbed film is not permanent. To get a permanent film, the adsorbed substances should be irreversibly precipitated at the interface, as was suggested by Ramsden (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1903, **A** 72, 156). Proteid solutions like egg-albumin can be denatured or irreversibly precipitated on air-liquid interface by violent agitation and this type of precipitation produces a permanent coating on an oil-water interface. Addition of salt solutions to the emulsion stabilised with egg-albumin cannot break the film round the oil particle; but the case is just the reverse with films produced by emulsifiers of group (i). The difference in the nature of films produced by the emulsifiers of groups (i) and (ii) is quite evident and it indicates greater stability of film produced by group (ii).

Gum acacia, also, has got the property of forming a very tough film round the oil particle and this is evidenced by the fact that when an emulsion is prepared with the help of about 10% of gum acacia, the emulsion even on drying on water-bath does not liberate free oil and the dry mass on moistening with water produces a finely dispersed emulsion.

Our experimental results show that when emulsifiers of group (i), which produce low surface tension, are mixed with gum acacia, they hinder the formation of a permanent film and thereby antagonise against the action of gum acacia. Only when the percentage of gum acacia is excessively high so as to supersede the antagonistic effect of low surface tension, we get a stable film.

The effect of bile salts against gum acacia is the most striking. When one per cent of bile salt is used alone, a very finely grained (1 to 5μ) emulsion is obtained, but when it is associated with gum acacia, the emulsion cracks no sooner it comes out of the colloid mill. Even as high as ten per cent of gum acacia could not produce any stable emulsion. When the percentage of the bile salt is as low as 0.1, emulsification is possible.

The effect of emulsifiers of group (ii) such as egg-albumin and saponin, is not antagonistic against gum acacia as is apparent from what has been said above. All of them form tough films at the interface and therefore mixtures of these emulsifiers produce better emulsion.

The effect of gum tragacanth, agar agar and Irish moss in presence of gum acacia is interesting. The emulsions prepared with the three emulsifiers separately are very thick and coarsely dispersed and water separated slowly on standing. It indicates that viscosity alone is not the only criterion of stability of an emulsion. These emulsifiers are only thickening agents and are poorly adsorbed. Although 0.8% of tragacanth converts the emulsion to W-O, it does not antagonise with gum acacia probably for its low adsorbability. It is, however, observed that increasing additions of gum acacia along with these thickening agents produce less viscous emulsion and at a certain stage the emulsion becomes so thin that water separates rapidly. The liquefying action of neutral salts on agar jelly is well known. The same type of liquefaction is obtained by the action of gum acacia on agar agar, gum tragacanth and Irish moss.

When gum tragacanth is used with bile salts, there was no immediate cracking of emulsion as with gum acacia. By offering viscosity,

gum tragacanth stabilises the bile salt emulsion for longer periods but the separation of oil at the top in the long run is not prevented.

TABLE III

Thickening effect of gum tragacanth.

Gum fraga.	Bile salt.	Remarks.
0.5%	0.05%	Cracks rapidly.
0.5	0.5	Cracks less rapidly.
0.5	1.0	Fine; oil separates very slowly.
1.0	1.0	Coarse; oil separates slowly from the beginning.
Lecithin.		
0.5	0.1	Cracks rapidly.
0.5	0.5	Oil separates very slowly.
1.0	0.5	Oil separates slowly from the beginning.
Egg-albumin.		
0.5	0.1	Little or no oil or water separates.
1.0	0.1	Oil separates from the beginning.
Turkey Red.		
0.5	0.75	Oil separates slowly from the beginning.
1.0	0.75	„ rapidly „ „
Gelatin.		
0.5	0.05	Coarse, oil separates from the beginning.
0.5	0.4	Thick, Fine; no oil or water separates.
1.0	0.4	Oil separates from the beginning.
Saponin.		
0.5	0.04	Fine, thick, no oil or water separates.
1.0	0.04	Oil separates from the beginning.

TABLE IV.

Emulsions with several other combinations.

Bile salt	1.0%	Irish Moss	1.0%	Oil and water separate from beginning.
Sodium oleate	0.2	"	1.5	" separate rapidly "
Turkeyred oil	0.75	Agar agar	0.4	" " slowly "
Egg-albumin	0.1	Lecithin	0.5	Thin " " "

From what has been said above, the general conclusion can be drawn that emulsifiers of the group (i) antagonise with the other groups and cause liberation of free oil at the top. Emulsifiers of the groups (ii), (iii) and (iv) do not have mutual antagonistic action. If however a large amount of gum acacia is used with emulsifiers of group (iii), the emulsions lose consistency, become thin and water separates at the bottom quickly.

Investigations on the change of physical and chemical properties of mixtures of emulsifying agents are now in progress.

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